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A STUDY ON WOMEN SELF-HELP GROUPS ON THE LIVELIHOOD CONDITIONS AND THEIR RURAL ECONOMY CONCERNING THOOTHUKUDI DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to enumerate the observation of the Women Self Help Group on the livelihood circumstances of the rural poor people in the Thoothukudi District. The present sources were collected through primary sources and secondary sources. The main data were collected with the assistance of the specially collected Interview Schedule. In this study, Stratified Proportionate sampling techniques methods were used. 200 sample women's self-help group people were selected for this study. The secondary sources were composed of Journals, Books, Reports, Newspapers, and the like to substantiate this study and as supportive evidence in the field of study. The observation on the evaluation identified the field-level visit to various women's self-help groups. This is focused on the significance of the rural economy. It denotes the significance of empowering the rural communities' potential power. The women's self-help group is competent in various problems and how they rectified their problems is also analyzed in this article. At present the manpower of women plays a very significant role in our country's development. Women's self-help groups give more energy and positive vibes to their members.

KEYWORDS: Rural Economy, Rural Poor, Living Condition, and Impact

INTRODUCTION

In our country, a major portion of the income is generated from rural communities. Rural women play a significant role in this particular task. Women's self-help groups play an important role in the nation's income. The women's self-help group creates opportunities for employment in all age groups of women. At present women know the importance of income and also they play a crucial role in developing their families as well as their country's income. Nowadays women know the importance of education. This education helps to improve their knowledge and working capacity.

OBJECTIVES

- Analyze the full view of the Women's self-help group on the livelihood conditions of the rural women in Thoothukudi district.
- To identify the problems faced by rural poor Women's self-help groups.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study aims to enumerate the process of the Women's self-help group on the livelihood conditions of rural women of the Thoothukudi district. These data were collated from primary and secondary sources. The primary sources involve the specially prepared Interview Schedule. All the sources are collected

from a considerable sample of Women's Self-help groups from the Thoothukudi district. Stratified Proportionate sampling techniques methods were used. 200 samples of rural poor were selected for the study. The inferior data was together from Journals, Books, Reports, Newspapers, and the like to substantiate the and as supportive pieces of evidence in the field of study.

DATA ANALYSIS

A Women's Self-help Group on the Livelihood Condition Regarding Age-wise Classification

The livelihood conditions of women play an important role in the development of the nation. Regarding the age factor, their lifestyle differs from one to another. For this present study, the ANOVA method was applied and identified the unfound hypothesis of no major relationship between livelihood and age-wise classification of the women self-help group in the Thoothukudi district. The resulting mean attained among the rural poor of different age-wise classifications on the status and the personal 'F' statistics are presented in Table 1.1 below.

Table – 1.1

Impact of Women's Self-help Group on the Livelihood Condition Regarding Age-wise Classification

Sl. No	Impact of Women Self Help Group on the livelihood condition	Mean Score Regarding Age –wise classification				F Statistics
		Below 25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	
1.	Living conditions	3.4345	3.1429	3.2182	3.0417	2.246
2.	Savings	3.4286	3.2857	3.3455	2.8750	1.855
3.	Self-confidence	3.2024	3.4643	3.0727	3.1667	1.086
4.	Medical care	3.0958	3.1071	3.8364	3.0000	1.015
5.	Repayment of loans	3.0833	3.1045	3.0909	3.0417	0.021
6.	Family expenses	3.5000	3.7143	3.7273	3.1667	2.602*
7.	Decision-making skills	3.3333	3.3214	3.5273	3.0417	1.226
8.	Economic independence	3.3214	2.9286	3.2727	3.2500	1.029
9.	Earning opportunities	3.3810	3.1071	3.3636	3.4583	0.524
10.	Household income	3.3452	3.6786	3.0182	3.0417	4.000*

Source: Primary sources

Five per cent level significant*

Table 1.1 inference the score of the mean regarding age-wise classification of the women self-help group. Based on the collected sources the age below 25 years contributes to their family expenditure and living conditions of the survival of this relevant mean score are 3.5000 and 3.4345. In the age group between 26 – 35 contributing their family expenses and their household income, the relevant mean score are 3.7143 and 3.6786. In this age group of people 36 – 45 years are contributing medical care and family expenses based on these sources regarding mean scores are 3.8364 and 3.7273. In this age group above 45 contributing to their family are earning opportunities and economic dependence, these relevant scores of the mean are 3.4583 and 3.2500.

Regarding the overall view of the women Self-help groups on the living conditions of the age-wise classification, the important differences are identified in the connection of contribution to their family expenditure and household income. The relevant 'F' statistics are major significant at a five percent level the null hypothesis was discarded.

The impact of Self-help Groups on Living Conditions is classified as Religious.

To indicate the major difference in the overall view of women's self-help groups on the livelihood conditions on the women's self-help group of different religious groups of people. ANOVA was worked out with the null hypothesis as there is no most important difference in the analysis view of the women's Self-help Group on the livelihood condition and the religion-wise source on the women's self-help group in Thoothukudi district.

Impact of Women's Self-help group on the livelihood Conditions regarding the classification of education level

To indicate the significant difference in the impact of women's self-help groups on the livelihood conditions regarding the women self-help group regarding the different education, ANOVA was attempted with the null hypothesis as there is no considerable difference in the impact of women's self-help groups on the livelihood condition among the different education of women self-help group in Thoothukudi district. The consequential mean score of the women self-help group of different education on the status and the relevant 'F' statistics are presented in below Table 1.2

Table – 1.2

Impact of the Women self-help group on the livelihood condition regarding the education level classification

Sl. No	Impact of Women self help respondents and their livelihood condition	Education wise classification (Mean Score among the Respondents)				F Statistics
		Uneducated	Level of Primary School	Level of Middle School	Level of high School	
1.	Living conditions	3.1905	3.3627	3.1892	3.3750	0.560
2.	Savings	3.3810	3.3109	3.1081	3.2917	0.457
3.	Self-confidence	3.3333	3.3834	3.1892	3.3145	0.329
4.	Medical care	3.6190	3.1917	3.0270	3.3333	0.998
5.	Repayment of loans	3.2381	3.0260	3.0541	2.9167	0.419
6.	Family expenses	3.4286	3.4093	3.5405	3.8333	1.580
7.	Decision-making skills	3.2852	3.3990	3.1351	3.2917	0.698
8.	Economic independence	2.9048	3.3420	3.2432	3.0000	1.553
9.	Earning opportunities	2.9524	3.4093	3.3243	2.9500	2.506*
10.	Household income	2.9025	3.2487	3.2973	3.1000	1.491

Source: Primary data

Table 1.2 shows the educational level categorization of the women's self-help group regarding their livelihood conditions. Based on this survey the uneducated data shows the women's self-help group contributing medical care and their family expenses and their relevant means score are 3.6190 and 3.4286. This survey shows their primary level education and their contributing are decision-making skills and family expenses and their scores of mean are 3.4093 and 3.3990. Based on these sources middle school women's self-help group data contributing to their family expenses and household income and their relevant means score are 3.5405 and 3.2973. The sources of high school data show the women self-help group of rural poor livelihood contributing to their family expenses and living conditions of the respondents and their relevant scores of mean are 3.8333 and 3.3750.

Regarding the educational level-wise classification of women self-help groups on the livelihood conditions, the important differences among the dissimilar education of rural poor, are identified in the view of earning opportunities since the relevant 'F' statistics is important at a five percent level and the null hypothesis is discarded.

Problems in women's self-help group regarding the age-wise classification

To identify the significant dissimilarity in the troubles in women's self-help among different age-wise groups of a women self-help group in the Thoothukudi district, verify the variance (ANOVA) was applied with the null hypothesis as "There is no major dissimilarity in the issues faced by the women self-help group all among different age wise groups of rural poor in Thoothukudi district". The resulting mean score of the categorization of age of the women self-help group the respective 'F' statistics are explained in Table 1.3

Table -1. 3
Problems in a Women Self-help Group and Age-wise Classification -ANOVA

Sl. No	Problems faced by the women self help group	Age wise classification (Mean Score)				F Statistics
		Less than 25 years	26-35 years	36-45 years	Above 46 years	
1.	In sufficient crèche facility for kids	3.2211	3.3324	3.2320	3.4135	2.133
2.	In sufficient shading tents during the break period	3.3654	3.5056	3.3944	3.5193	1.747
3.	Toiletry facilities	3.1073	3.2986	3.2807	3.4808	3.209*
4.	In sufficient safe drinking water	3.0395	3.2056	3.1614	3.3654	2.149
5.	Delayed response	3.3652	3.5140	3.4548	3.5962	2.696*
6.	Bribe	3.6049	3.8006	3.6441	3.8462	4.904*
7.	Unpleasant attitude	3.5769	3.7768	3.7360	3.8077	3.374*

8.	Non-availability of first aid facility	3.5763	3.7725	3.6299	4.0000	2.532*
9.	Distance place of employment	3.6667	3.8112	3.7416	3.9327	2.637*
10.	Job card misused by the other person	3.4394	3.5791	3.5790	3.6154	1.072

Source: Computed Data

The above table 1.3 shows the various troubles faced by the women's self-help group, for this data the age level of less than 25 years of the women's self-help group people mostly faced problems with bribes and distance place of employment and their respective scores of mean are 3.6049 and 3.6667. Regarding the age group of 26- 35, the women self-help group people faced problems are distance place of employment, and unpleasant attitudes their respective scores of mean were 3.7416 and 3.7360. Regarding the age group above 46 years, the women's self-help group faced the problems of are non-availability of a first aid facility and distance place of employment and their respective scores of mean are 4.0000 and 3.9327.

The collected sources of problems faced by the women's self-help group, people meet various problems the major differences among the different age-wise classifications of women self-help group are identified they are late response, bribes, unlikable attitude, insufficient first aid facility, a distance of employment, low-level payment for injury cases, and no availability of toiletry facilities, since the relevant 'F' statistics are major at 5 percent level, the null hypothesis is discarded.

Problems in women's self-help groups among the different marital status-wise classification

To exhibit the major dissimilarity in the issues faced by the women self-help group regarding the different marital statuses of the women self-help group respondents of the Thoothukudi district, the study of variance (ANOVA) was calculated with the null hypothesis, "There is no major dissimilarity in issues faced by the women self-help group in Thoothukudi district". The resulting mean score based on the different marital status classifications of women's self-help group and the relevant 'F' statistics are shown in below Table 1.4

Table - 1.4

Problems faced by the women's self-help regarding the different marital status classifications - ANOVA

Sl. No	Problems faced by the women self help group	Marital Status wise classification (Mean Score)			F Statistics
		Married	Unmarried	Widow	
1.	In sufficient crèche facility for kids	3.1026	3.0514	3.3668	7.347*
2.	In sufficient shading tents during the break period	3.4679	3.4263	3.5256	0.461
3.	Toiletry facilities	3.3636	3.2495	3.7564	5.412*

4.	In sufficient drinking water	3.2759	3.1557	3.4487	4.260*
5.	Delayed response	3.5688	3.3738	3.7089	6.539*
6.	Bribe	3.7844	3.6377	3.9620	5.078*
7.	Unpleasant attitude	3.7250	3.7033	3.7722	0.247
8.	Insufficient first aid facility	3.8156	3.6120	3.9747	3.441*
9.	Distance place of employment	3.7563	3.7118	4.1139	6.514*
10.	Misused by job card	3.5078	3.4993	3.8861	3.784*

Source: Computed Data

Five per cent level significant*

Table 1.4 shows the problems faced by women's self-help groups regarding their marital status-wise classification. Regarding the data of married women faced problems in non availability of first aid facilities and bribes, based on this data and their relevant mean scores are 3,8156 and 3.7844. On the other side, the unmarried women faced problems are distance place of employment, and unpleasant attitudes, and the relevant scores of mean were 3.7118 and 3.7033. Regarding the data of the widows women self-help group people faced the problems are distance of employment and the non availability of first aid facility and the relevant scores of mean are 4.1139 and 3.9747.

The collected data regarding the problems in a women's self-help group, the important difference among the different marital statuses wise categorization of women self-help group, are identified the late response, bribes, first aid facility, distance of employment, job cards misused insufficient facility of creche toilet facility not available and insufficient of drinking water, since the relevant 'F' statistics are major at percent level, the null hypothesis is discarded.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on this sources the following recommendations are expected for the women's self-help group they are listed below,

- The remuneration is fixed by the government is not enough the self-help group people expect the revise remuneration.
- The working times are not specified, some time the working hours increase based on the completion of work. Therefore fixed working hours are needed.
- Distance place of employment is another one of the issues, the transport facility is sometimes insufficient. The organizer need to concentrate sufficient transport facilities for women self-help group people.
- Drinking and toilet facilities are essential. Need more concentration for this one.
- The people expect the crèche facility for their kids. It's also important one of the suggestions.

CONCLUSION

Women's self-help provides employment opportunities for women. It's very helpful for their running family, and also it helps the growth of the nation's economy. The self-help women feel self-confident and present. Women are not dependent on anyone. On the other hand, the number of working days is very low.

the government is trying to increase the working days. The remuneration is comparatively low for male workers so revised remuneration is also needed. The growth of women not only helps their families but also helps the progress of our nation.

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